

USE OF INFORMATION AND TELECOMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN DISTANCE EDUCATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: In this article, the article discusses the use of information and telecommunication technologies in distance learning technologies.

Keywords: Distance education, scientific, pedagogical, information and communication, educational process, educational service, information and telecommunication.

Distance education technologies are aimed at organizing the process of interaction between students and teachers using information and telecommunication technologies. The keyword "interaction" in this context defines and emphasizes the success of the implementation of the learning process by the teacher and the student. Organized interaction of the participants of the educational process using distance education technologies is the main and important factor of learning. It is important to understand the need to create a unique educational content that will be the basis for the implementation of distance education, to develop methodological equipment for distance education, and to have special training for teachers.

The next feature is related to the process of adaptation of the teacher to new working conditions. This is a traditional pedagogical technique. It becomes unnecessary for the teacher or undergoes changes. This is the question, the answer to which each teacher must search for himself. Constant pedagogical search for new forms and methods of work is imposed on the teacher's daily workload. As a result, this issue is either not addressed at all, or the applied forms of work do not correspond to the course objectives [14].

In this article, in order to improve the quality of education, the subject and hypotheses of the object have been developed:

- theoretical justification of the pedagogical interaction of the subjects of the educational process in the conditions of distance education;
- determining teaching methods in distance education, taking into account the identified features of pedagogical interaction;
- development of an author's course that reveals the features of pedagogical interaction of the participants of the educational process in the conditions of distance education, holding a section for approving the module and determining its effectiveness in pedagogical interaction;
- development of methodological recommendations on effective pedagogical cooperation in the conditions of distance education.

In order to effectively implement mutual cooperation in the context of distance education, it is necessary to create certain conditions that help:

- active involvement of all participants of the educational process in the discussion and performance of tasks;

- organization of collaborative research;
- implementation of continuous communication (synchronous and asynchronous means of communication);
- develop empathy and reasoning [15].

Bespalko VP the computer "can be considered as a participant in the teaching and learning process along with the teacher" . Of course, we are talking about an automated learning system that includes a computer as a technical support.

Harmonization, mutual adaptation and mutual enrichment of these scientific disciplines, combined with a single goal of increasing the effectiveness of multifaceted educational activities, is not only difficult in itself, but also is a new task for lim".

"Distance education is an education organized in accordance with the curriculum, which is usually carried out in a different place. The location of the teacher and, as a result, a special methodology for creating a curriculum, special teaching methods, special communication methods and technologies also require a special organizational-administrative structure" [17]. The information-educational environment of distance education - means of information transfer, information resources, aimed at meeting the educational needs of users is a systematically organized set of communication protocols, technical, software and organizational-methodological support". Education is a specially organized process of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities, and education is the result of training, education and development of a person. AA Andreev considers this definition to be learning through interaction with distance learning resources and educational subjects organized with the help of information technologies and telecommunications. Yu.V. Golovanova, for example, notes the transition of society's development from the technology sphere to the information sphere, and considers the information sphere as a combination of basic knowledge and innovative information that is constantly updated and changed.

Adoption of the concept of creation and development of a unified system of distance education in Uzbekistan contributed to wide coverage of the problem of distance education in scientific literature . The Law "On Education of Uzbekistan" defines concepts such as "e-learning" and "distance learning technologies". The concept includes the first official definition of the term "distance education", describes its main principles. Legislation strengthening the possibilities of using distance education serves to accumulate theoretical and practical experience in the implementation of the distance education system in higher education institutions.[6]

In the field of distance education, innovation takes a strong place and becomes a competitive form of higher education along with traditional forms of education. The advantages of using this form of education are clear:

Currently, serious attention is paid to the search for all types of educational forms that meet all the requirements for the educational process. Distance education is recognized as a fairly effective form of education. Therefore, distance education is being emphasized as the only form of education that can maintain its effectiveness despite various circumstances and force majeure in the world. But the difficulties of implementing traditional work forms and methods in a computer environment require the search for clear and new solutions. University students face and face challenges in using distance

learning in their professional activities. In order to meet all the requirements for professors and teachers, it is already necessary to create the conditions for acquiring the skills of working in distance education at the university [18]. In order to improve the entire educational system, it was found necessary to prepare teachers for activities in distance education.

Definitions were clarified as part of this study

"distance learning" and "pedagogical interaction". The term that reflects the whole nature of distance education was adopted as the basis for this study. This is a training in which all educational processes are carried out using modern information and telecommunication technologies with the territorial dispersion of teachers and students. The information-educational environment of distance education plays an important role, which includes data transmission tools, information resources, interaction protocols, hardware, software and organizational-methodical support, user support. aimed at meeting the needs of the community. An automated educational system in which a computer acts as a technical component provides conditions for the organization of pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education.[19]

Pedagogical cooperation in the conditions of distance education is considered as a specially organized process aimed at solving educational tasks. Organization of mutual cooperation in distance education requires professional skills and significant time resources. If all educational activities are carried out on the basis of the strategy of developing the influence of the teacher on students, this process will be effective if it should be organized according to the purpose.

Pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education is characterized by features that indicate the presence of unstudied moments in pedagogical practice. Among them:

- technical organization of the educational process;
- asynchronous type of communication;
- long-term adaptation to work and study in distance education;
- increase the share of independent education of students;
- the emergence of additional tasks for the teacher in the form of support of

the educational process by the tutor.

Each of these problems carries out special tasks that determine the choice of methods and tools that allow for pedagogical interaction in the context of distance education.

Teaching methods that serve to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education have been determined. Active and interactive teaching methods (business game, brainstorming, master class, case method, etc.) have a special place.[20]

Also, methods that reflect the specific characteristics of mutual relations in the conditions of territorial dispersion of teachers and students - online consultations, offline consultations, online video lectures, offline video lectures, interactive computer video lectures, seminars.

Based on the analysis of the activity of the teacher in the organization of pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education, the fifth type of interaction in the conditions of distance education - "teacher - distance education system" was determined.

This led to the conclusion that it is important to combine all five types of interactions to create an effective learning process.[21]

The creation of the author's course "Peculiarities of pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education" helps to acquire practical skills for the implementation of pedagogical interaction, which is necessary for successful operation in the new educational conditions. The course is structured in such a way that it reflects all the main features of the teacher's activity in the context of distance education, reveals the essence of distance education and aims to gain primary experience in the organization of pedagogical interaction, because it combines learning with both. traditional format and computer use. Active and interactive methods of working online are to bring students' knowledge closer to the real conditions of professional activity[1].

The variety of active and interactive methods of teaching fills the educational process with personally significant forms of work (virtual laboratory, case method, tasks-simulators, discussions) for interest and motivation. One of the important and comprehensive modules of the authorship course in terms of practical material content is the module "Pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education".

Students receive the necessary information that allows them to move between different methods of interaction and adapt the forms of organizing pedagogical interaction within the framework of traditional education to working conditions in the distance education format.

University students have their own views on the use of certain teaching methods, and in this regard, there is an opportunity to put their practical skills into practice in the distance learning environment. In this regard, cooperation between teachers and students is being organized through active and interactive teaching methods.

In order to determine the effectiveness of the author's course "Specific features of pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education" with students of the 4th year of the "Psychological-pedagogical education" course, a section was carried out on the classes developed in the course increased. , which reflected a positive trend in the following indicators:

"enthusiasm", "independence", "professional flexibility",

"professional self-awareness", "communication", "cognitive needs" and "creative orientation".

Due to the combination of different forms of work (traditional education and distance education format), students are given the opportunity to gain experience in pedagogical cooperation, an adequate attitude to distance education is formed, and a clear understanding of the teacher's duties in teaching is formed[42]. Such conditions. Under the condition of applying the course to the educational process of the university, students will acquire the basic skills of organizing pedagogical cooperation in a remote environment.

training and improving their professional skills. The cutting result is developed confirms the effectiveness of the authorship course.

The above allows us to emphasize that the tasks set in the research have been solved and the goal has been achieved.[2]

The research conducted cannot solve all the problems related to the organization of pedagogical interaction in distance education. The conclusions obtained in the course of

the research reveal the need to determine the educational possibilities of interactive teaching methods in the organization of pedagogical interaction, to further study pedagogical interaction in the conditions of distance education.

If the didactic possibilities of the teaching methods are fully disclosed, and if it is possible to learn the mechanisms of the organization of effective pedagogical cooperation, as well as the adaptation of teaching methods to distance education, the practical significance of the research will be deeper.

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